

The Role of Communicative Competence in Developing the English Language Proficiency of Electronics Engineering Students through Communicative Language Teaching

JC Faith S. Salvador¹, Mikaela T. Santos¹, Iya Mae S. Dizon¹, Florentino G. Pineda Jr.²

¹Bachelor of Science In Electronics Engineering, College of Engineering, Bulacan State University, Malolos City, 3000, Philippines

²Department of English, College of Arts and Letters, Bulacan State University, Malolos City, 3000, Philippines

Abstract

This research explores Communicative Language Teaching (CLT) and its role in developing English language proficiency of Electronics Engineering (ECE) students. English as a lingua franca plays a significant role in various fields of work, including Engineering. Therefore, it is imperative that their communication skills and language proficiency are developed accordingly. This study employs a quantitative approach in assessing the communicative competence of 220 Electronics Engineering students from Bulacan State University through a survey evaluating their grammar, discourse, sociolinguistic, and strategic competence. Results indicate an overall advanced level of communicative competence, justifying the role of Communicative Language Teaching as a tool for enhancing students' English language proficiency. Based on the interpretation of the statistics, the respondents can perform relatively well using English, signifying that

their communication skills can meet the demands of output-based performance, such as Engineering. In addition, the researchers suggest a further comprehensive study regarding the impact of CLT in Engineering assessing its effectiveness through its integration in classroom settings.

Keywords: Communicative Competence, Communicative Language Teaching (CLT), English Language Proficiency, Engineering, Electronics Engineering (ECE) students

Introduction

Communicative Language Teaching (CLT) is an educational tool that centers its instruction on language functions and well-developed conversational skills, particularly for students. Tian (2025) cites Qi Yi (2021), explaining that CLT highlights the significance of enhancing learners' ability to use a language effectively. Thus, it is also referred to as the notional-functional approach structuring a syllabus around real-life situations and choosing specific functions to prepare students to communicate in that situation. The function of CLT as a teaching tool emphasizes a significant impact in different academic settings that focus on language fluency rather than following language rules as stated by Qaserras (2023). These investigations underscore the significant impact of the Communicative Language Teaching in enhancing the language abilities of learners, particularly those studying engineering.

English proficiency is a crucial factor for the success of those in the Engineering field, as it impacts career, education, and an individual's influence on others. Engineering is a field that continuously evolves in response to technical advancements, as well as innovators in various paths within the community, affirming the significant role they play across borders and cultures. Therefore, the English language has officially become the lingua franca of the technological, scientific, and engineering realm. (Rani & Singh, 2023).

In the Philippines, there is a mandated law, known as the Enhanced Basic Education Act of

2013, stating that high school students must complete another two years of high school, called Senior High School (SHS), wherein they will be allowed to choose a specific strand that aligns with their preferred college program. In line with this, an engineering student is recommended to possess core knowledge in mathematical concepts and language fluency, which is taught under the Science, Technology, Engineering, and Mathematics (STEM) Strand. With these, the importance of English for Engineering students is substantial and vital in their professional attainment.

The findings of Salam and Luksfinanto (2024) present a geographic limitation as studies regarding CLT are conducted mostly on Western countries. Despite the implied importance of communication, very few studies regarding this issue have been made in the Philippines, if not conducted with Engineering students in general as their population, lacking data that solely focuses on Electronics Engineering students. This strengthens the need to conduct a study that not only aims to improve technical skills but also integrates effective strategies to improve interpersonal communication proficiency that is essential to the workplace, as suggested by Abides (2024). Enhancing such skills greatly contributes to Electronics Engineering students' employment by bridging the gap in competencies required in the field.

In accordance with this, Acuna-Villacorte (2025) highlights a dedicated specialized language program for Electronics Engineering, intertwining it with terms such as CLT and

learner-centeredness. It is stated that these students must display commendable communication skills, as it is vital in their field of work. To achieve this, universities and colleges must evaluate and create a course related to performing their communicative competence with practicality and professionalism.

Although methods have been studied to increase engineering communication skills, including Outcome-Based Education (OBE), there are not enough studies examining Communicative Language Teaching (CLT) among Filipino engineering students, much more in a specific field such as Electronics Engineering. However, studies from other countries such as India, including the works of Mayavan (2022) and Venkateswara and John (2017), state positive responses from engineering students as CLT is integrated into their education. In line with these, this study will assess the communicative competence of Electronics Engineering (ECE) students to evaluate the integration of CLT.

According to Shukla (2024) English communication skills are crucial for academic excellence, employability, and for career advancement for those who are in the engineering field. These communication skills can be measured through students' communicative competence, which comprises grammar, discourse, sociolinguistic, and strategic competences (Baustista, R.A. & Del Valle, J.M., 2022).

The communicative approach fosters realistic

practices of using a language to ensure communicative competence. In a field such as engineering, it is essential to demonstrate language proficiency in professional settings. Thus, applying and utilizing CLT will positively impact the English Language skills of engineering students. Moreover, Badawy (2023) investigated and stated in his study various English language skills of Engineering students, and recommends these following insights: (1) Implement a curriculum that includes communicative skills, proper and technical writing, vocabulary expansion, and reading comprehension; (2) the curriculum should be applied by competent instructors who have a background in language teaching; (3) advocate the curriculum to engineering students and emphasize its significance; and lastly, (4) assure that the curriculum meets the need and expected outcome of its application. It is affirmed that an English curriculum offers a great amount of help for Engineering courses, further strengthening their communication skills and future in engineering.

Conceptual Framework

This study is anchored on Dell Hymes' Theory of Communicative Competence (1972) and Michael Canale and Merrill Swain's model of Communicative Competence (1980), which provides the framework for both the assessment of the electronics engineering students' current abilities and the implied integration of Communicative Language Teaching (CLT). The emergence of this theory began as a critique of Noam Chomsky's Language Acquisition Theory (1965) regarding his idea of competence and

performance. Hymes emphasizes the term "communicative competence", encompassing a broader concept which includes proficiency in the language use in terms of linguistics and sociolinguistic competence (Fauziati, 2015). This highlights the ability to use language proficiently in actual conversation across contexts, presenting a holistic approach to communication. Hyme's theory was further expanded by Canale and Swain's communicative competence theory (1980), including components of communicative competence such as grammatical competence, sociolinguistic competence, discourse competence and strategic competence (Tian, 2025). These components facilitate the ability to deliver clear, relevant information while adjusting to the context, ensuring comprehension despite communication barriers, which are skills that are essential for real-world application, particularly in technical fields.

Following this framework, the aim of Communicative Language Teaching is to develop strategies to improve language skills which are deemed significant in taking on everyday situations, thus enhancing communicative competence (Tian, 2025). The relevance of communicative competence to CLT has been well established, with studies demonstrating a positive effect as it is integrated, enhancing language fluency, engagement and effective real-life application (Salam & Luksfinanto, 2024). As a pedagogical approach, CLT is specifically designed to foster practical language application, emphasizing the importance of cultivating language fluency

rather than its prescriptive application. This approach is particularly applicable for students in a technical field such as Electronics Engineering, which highly emphasizes the role of effective communication. Therefore, the integration of CLT into the educational setting is likely to enhance the students' language use, which corresponds with their communicative competence.

Research Objectives

This study primarily aims to identify the relation of Communicative Language Teaching and Electronics Engineering students through gathering data regarding their communicative competence in utilizing English language. In the Philippines, English is the primary language exercised in business, law, academe, and formal events involving professionals from numerous fields. As stated by Santos, et. al (2022), Philippines is globally recognized as an English-speaking nation, with English as one of the country's official languages along with Filipino. However, as reported on EF English Proficiency Index, Test of English for International Communication (TOEIC), there is a noticeable decline in English language proficiency in the nation. This is evident in multiple reports throughout the years where the country's rank fell from 14th to 20th place in 2018 to 2019, then dropped again in 27th place in the year 2020. In line with these, it is vital to provide proper measurements to aid dilemmas, including this English language proficiency deterioration among Filipinos. Thus, this research indicates the importance of identifying different strategies, such as CLT, in improving communicative competence

through language proficiency of Filipino ECE students. Furthermore, the study's objective also includes providing additional information in the area of CLT and its integration in Electronics Engineering, as the researchers noticed the lack of resources regarding the stated variables.

Significance of the Study

This research intends to utilize its objective in assessing students, faculties, universities, and curriculum developers in providing platforms for students to develop their communicative competence. The research prioritizes the connection of Communicative Language Teaching and students' communicative skills, particularly from the program of Electronics Engineering, therefore identifying learning methods that might improve learners' competence in performing English as a language. In addition, CLT is a significant teaching strategy mostly applied by various faculties to demonstrate communicative skills in their classes. Moreover, universities and curriculum developers may employ and devise strategic-learning components integrating CLT in curriculums concerning students across the university, especially for those in technical fields, such as Engineering, wherein performance and outcomes are valued.

Scope and Delimitation

This study investigates the communicative competence of Electronics Engineering students which is anchored on the suggested implementation of Communicative Language Teaching. The researchers specifically survey

Electronics Engineering students, ranging from first to fourth year, studying at Bulacan State University. These students are deemed suitable for the study as communication skills, interpersonal abilities, and language learning are important aspects often used in their field, especially when aiming to be globally competitive.

On the other hand, the study has a few limitations. Only a handful of Electronics Engineering students are chosen to participate and a quantitative approach is applied due to the time constraints faced by the researchers. Furthermore, Salam and Luksfinanto (2024) states a downside of using a qualitative approach as interpretations may contain bias, and highlighted the opportunity to utilize a quantitative approach for a much comprehensive understanding of the impact of CLT on language proficiency.

In addition, since the study is conducted on students of Bulacan State University, the data gathered might not be applicable to students from different schools and geographic locations. Since this is a quantitative study, the researchers are only able to obtain numerical data and are not able to gain a deeper understanding of the students' individual perspectives. Moreover, the study solely focused on the development of English language proficiency instead of language proficiency in general.

Review of Related Studies

Numerous studies globally have examined the English language courses, specifically in the

engineering field. In Bangladesh for instance, the study of Bhuiyan, M.S.S.(2019) found that engineering students have a low level of English proficiency that is necessary for academic success and effective interpersonal communication. Similarly, a study from Khan and Buiyan (2024) mentioned that many engineering students lack confidence in their presentation skills. Due to these findings, they suggested revising the curricula, integrating communication and presentation courses, and having continuous communicative activities that can address the challenges of students.

Despite reforms of the Philippine curriculum and English being its second official language, a gradual decline in the nation's proficiency has been observed based on the results of EF English Proficiency Index (EF EPI) and Test of English for International Communication (TOEIC) throughout the years. Building on these international findings, some studies focus specifically on Electronics Engineering students' communicative competence in the Philippines, highlighting similar challenges. A research from Sitoy and Sonsona (2024) advocates for innovative and communicative approaches in language instruction. Their study recommended the use of Communicative Language Teaching (CLT) in enhancing the students' communication and language proficiency, emphasizing its effectiveness in improving both students' communication skills and critical thinking.

English Language Proficiency is important for Engineers for effective performance in their

jobs. The chances of getting a job rely heavily on the level of proficiency in communication skills of a person. In most engineering organizations, graduates are expected to carry out their technical, administrative, and other tasks using the English Language (Shrestha et. al., 2019). In line with this, a study from Abides, R.J. (2024) highlights the importance of communication and other soft skills needed in the electronics industry in managing electronic systems, communication, collaboration, and professionalism.

In summary, studies and literature globally regarding the English Language Proficiency of the students have been conducted and the lack of required proficiency for academic and interpersonal success were found. Similar recommendations such as curriculum revision, implementing communicative activities, testing innovative training methods, etc. were mentioned. Though there is an evident decrease in the Philippine's level of proficiency of students, some local studies suggested an approach like CLT in improving skills in communication and critical thinking. It is highly significant, especially in engineering to have a high level of proficiency to be able to adapt and excel in this field.

Methods

Research Design

This research employed a quantitative method in examining and identifying patterns regarding communicative competence, language proficiency, CLT, and ECE students. Quantitative Research, defined by Bandhari (2020), is the process of assessing gathered

numerical data, providing predictions, and testing hypotheses in relation to the identified mean and patterns that will demonstrate a large population.

This study utilized a descriptive design, particularly a survey questionnaire, in determining the communicative competence of Electronics Engineering students. According to McCombes (2019), descriptive research is widely used in describing a phenomenon, situation, or population. It is utilized in finding answers to what, where, when, and how questions, however it cannot provide data regarding why questions. In this design, variables are not controlled nor manipulated by the researchers, the sole purpose is to measure or observe the given variables. Thus, the study only states the communicative competence of ECE students in a descriptive manner.

Participants

The participants of the study included Electronics Engineering students from first year to fourth year from Bulacan State University. This specific field was chosen due to a limitation found in the literature concerning English language proficiency among Electronics Engineering students. Moreover, the researchers utilized simple random sampling to identify their respondents. Simple random sampling is a sampling technique utilized with respondents which possess similar characteristics and are equally represented (Noor, Tajik, & Golzar, 2022). This technique was chosen despite the

difference in academic exposure since the respondents were associated with the same field.

The researchers utilized Slovin's formula to determine the needed sample from the population. Slovin's Formula calculates the required sample sizes when the population is too large to directly sample every member. This was also applied and works for simple random sampling (Ellen, 2022). Using this formula, it was found that the student needed roughly two-hundred twenty (220) students from the overall four-hundred ninety (490) Electronics Engineering students. To ensure the accuracy of the calculated sample size, the researchers utilized a Raosoft sample size calculator. McCrum-Gardner (2010), as cited in McCrum-Gardner (2024), Raosoft Calculator is a sample size calculator used to achieve a desired level of accuracy by determining the right number of needed respondents in a research. The solution shows almost similar results, confirming the sample size to consist of two-hundred twenty (220) Electronics Engineering students.

Research Instrument

The data-gathering procedure used by the researchers involved systematic distribution of survey questionnaires to a randomized number of electronics engineering students in different year levels at Bulacan State University. This method was strictly designed to ensure the representation of a diverse cross-section of the student body. Through this structured approach, the researchers aimed to gain insights regarding the level of

communicative competence of the participants. The objective of the study is to assess the communicative competence of Electronics Engineering students, and identify the possible approach for CLT and its implementation. In order to achieve this, the study will utilize a 4-point Likert-scale questionnaire composed of four (4) components, including Grammar Competence, Discourse Competence, Sociolinguistic Competence, and Strategic Competence, composed of five (5) questions each component, totalling in 20 items. The Likert-scale questionnaire will allow respondents to express varying degrees of agreement, providing significant insights.

Moreover, the instrument is adapted and modified based on the study of Bautista and Del Valle (2023). To assure the validity of the instrument of this study, the survey is assessed and validated by three key experts in the field of communication and language, Electronics Engineering, and English language. The indicators were modified to better suit the purpose of the study. The modifications were made to enhance clarity on the use of the English language by integrating the term "English language" and by improving grammar. Utilizing the recommendation of the validators, examples for unfamiliar terminologies were provided to better facilitate understanding. With these, the data collection is assured to present reliable information with conformity in the research conducted.

Data Collection

In gathering data, the researchers utilized a descriptive survey method, which allows the study to present data regarding a particular phenomena by using a Likert scale questionnaire. This study employed communicative competence by identifying four (4) components that will assess the respondents of the research. The questionnaire is adapted, thus, in utilizing this, it is modified in accordance with this study, which focuses more on identifying the communicative competence of Electronics Engineering students, in order to determine if Communicative Language Teaching is suitable in developing their communicative skills. Furthermore, the instrument is then disseminated to two hundred nineteen (219) to two hundred twenty (220) Electronics Engineering students. The researchers utilized printed survey questionnaires for the data gathering. Ensuring a rapid and convenient, yet accurate response from the large number of population required in the study.

Ethical Consideration

In order to ensure amenability of the respondents and confidentiality of the gathered data, the researchers provided a consent form integrated in the survey questionnaire. The responses provided are utilized for the sole purpose of providing data for the study. Furthermore, the names and data of the Electronics Engineering students as the respondents are concealed to maintain their anonymity as the participants.

Data Analysis

To analyze the data, Google Sheets are utilized to determine the measures of central tendency, specifically the weighted mean. The results from this treatment was interpreted by means of using an ordinal scale, particularly a 4-point Likert Scale, to accurately interpret the results. 4 represents "strongly agree", 3 for "agree", 2 for "disagree", and 1 for "strongly disagree". A corresponding verbal interpretation was assigned according to its equivalent values from the scale. These interpretations were adapted from the study of Bautista and Del Valle (2023), wherein the following legends we used: 3.26 – 4.00 Expert; 2.51 – 3.25 Advanced; 1.76 – 2.50 Basic; 1.00 – 1.75 Needs Improvement. The application of these methods would contribute in assessing the respondent's measure of communicative competence in terms of grammar, discourse, sociolinguistic and strategic competence, ensuring reliable results.

Results

This section presents the communicative competence of Electronics Engineering students in terms of grammar competence, discourse competence, sociolinguistic competence and strategic competence. The analyzed and interpreted results were presented using tables, including the weighted mean and its verbal interpretation.

Table 1: Grammar Competence

Indicators	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation
1. I speak English fluently and accurately in most situations using verbal resources.	2.93	Advanced
2. I figure out how English words are broken into different sounds.	3.24	Advanced
3. I use English vocabulary to sufficiently express ideas and feelings.	3.02	Advanced
4. I use a clear voice and precise pronunciation of words with people.	2.91	Advanced
5. I select and use proper intonation.	3.11	Advanced
Composite Mean	3.04	Advanced

Indicators	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation
1. I speak English fluently and accurately in most situations using verbal resources.	2.93	Advanced
2. I figure out how English words are broken into different sounds.	3.24	Advanced
3. I use English vocabulary to sufficiently express ideas and feelings.	3.02	Advanced
4. I use a clear voice and precise pronunciation of words with people.	2.91	Advanced
5. I select and use proper intonation.	3.11	Advanced
Composite Mean	3.04	Advanced

Table 1 reveals that Electronics Engineering students demonstrate an advanced level of grammar competence, as reflected by a weighted mean of 3.04. This implies that the students possess enough mastery and knowledge of linguistics, specifically grammar rules. Such a level of competence indicates that the students are capable of facilitating proper conversation in English. Furthermore, this competence provides an advantage, as engineers utilize appropriate use of grammar when communicating in the global context or preparing technical reports and documents.

Table 2: Discourse Competence

Indicators	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation
1. I speak confidently in English in front of a small group or even a huge crowd.	2.52	Advanced
2. I interact spontaneously and confidently in formal or informal communicative situations using English.	2.83	Advanced

3. I value and respect the rules of oral interaction, gestures, and body language.	3.52	Expert
4. I express knowledge, facts, and opinions orally in English during presentations.	2.98	Advanced
5. I speak smoothly in English with no hesitation that does not interfere with communication.	2.55	Advanced
Composite Mean	2.88	Advanced

Table 2 shows that students possess an advanced level of discourse competence, yielding an average of 2.88. Students demonstrated awareness of appropriate speech delivery and the ability to construct a smooth flow of ideas. This competence enables them to properly convey and understand a message. Electronics engineering students utilize this skill as the field requires not only proficiency in the technical use of language but also structured communication. Possessing and advanced discourse competence may also contribute to their confidence while interacting with professionals.

Table 3: Sociolinguistic Competence

Indicators	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation
1. I can converse and interact harmoniously in English.	2.93	Advanced
2. I consider and give due respect to views and ideas.	3.50	Expert
3. I select suitable verbal as well as non-verbal means of expression in everyday situations, both inside and outside of the school.	3.26	Expert

4. I deliver a message with appropriate social meanings.	3.23	Advanced
5. I am familiar with the variety of English in different cultures.	3.06	Advanced
Composite Mean	3.20	Advanced

Table 3 shows that the level of sociolinguistic competence falls within the verbal interpretation of “advanced” with a weighted mean of 3.20. These results show that Electronics Engineering students are adept in being part of conversations, expressing their views, using the right expression and interpreting social meaning. Such competence is crucial in the field of Electronics Engineering where professionals must collaborate with diverse individuals from different cultures. However, some instances show students struggling to communicate efficiently using English Language to other people. The learners should practice more on using this language to be comfortable using it. Overall, it is found that students have a high level of Sociolinguistic Competence, which enable students to take part in the social context and use appropriate communication style.

Table 4: Strategic Competence

Indicators	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation
1. I employ a variety of communication techniques to make communication interesting and effective (e.g. active listening, asking questions, practice public speaking).	3.18	Advanced
2. I use non-verbal gestures to converse	3.27	Expert

and give emphasis to my message.		
3. I utilize a variety of sentence structures to stimulate the interest of the listeners.	3.12	Advanced
4. I adjust to the present communication situation accordingly.	3.21	Advanced
5. I can use the English language appropriately in different situations.	3.11	Advanced
Composite Mean	3.18	Advanced

Table 4 posits that the level of competence of the students under Strategic Competence obtained a weighted mean of 3.18, which falls under the interpretation of advance. The overall results are good and show that the respondents use diverse approaches in communicating. This proves their strategic competence, which is vital in the field they belong to, as they will need different ways of communicating based on the context they are in. It is also manifested that the students are expert in using non-verbal gestures in communicating, which helps them converse more effectively. However, a few show difficulty in utilizing a variety of sentence structures, which can hinder them from using appropriate sentences in different contexts. In summary, the students have high Strategic Competence, which shows that they have authentic ways of communicating, especially in their field.

Overall, Electronics Engineering students are advanced in communication. This excellent level of communicative competence provides an advantage, as effective communication is crucial to their field. Engineering in general

requires collaboration and teamwork. Thus, they can utilize this skill to properly communicate their ideas, both academically and professionally in the future.

Discussion

The findings showed that students are in the advanced levels of Grammar Competence, Discourse Competence, Sociolinguistic Competence, and Strategic Competence. This indicates that they are skilled in communicating effectively and are highly proficient in English which are aligned with the demands of academic and professional context in engineering. Though the respondents performed well overall, there are still minor challenges like figuring out how English words break down into sounds, improving skills in using varieties of sentence structures, maintaining confidence when speaking English in front of a crowd, and interacting comfortably using English language. These results suggest that integrating CLT as an approach in teaching could be beneficial for learners that have high proficiency in honing their communicative competence.

Meanwhile, it is important to consider that the result of this study is limited to ECE students within one institution, which means that it is not fully applicable to all engineering students or other academic settings. Still, the data collected supports integrating CLT-based activities that will strengthen their proficiency and prepare them for the demands of their profession in terms of communicative demands.

Conclusion

This study aimed to address a gap in the literature surrounding English language use through investigating communicative competence, specifically within the field of electronics engineering.

To gain a deeper understanding of the matter a survey was conducted to measure the communicative competence of the students. It was found that electronics engineering students generally possess a high level of communicative competence. This finding serves as an anchor for pedagogical intervention. With the students' advanced proficiency, the study strongly recommends the implementation of Communicative Language Teaching (CLT). Implementing CLT has practical implications for the development of curriculum and teaching methods, as integrating CLT-based activities can prepare ECE students to meet the demands of their professional field and further enhance their communication skills and competence.

Overall, this study presents valuable data, providing a holistic view of electronics engineering education. By focusing not only on their technical expertise but also on the importance of communication skills, this study emphasizes that proficiency in both aspects is essential to succeed in the electronics engineering profession.

Recommendations

The discussion and conclusion of the study suggest the following recommendations for further exploration of CLT and its impact in Engineering students communicative competence:

Curriculum development and Teaching Method. Based on the findings, Communicative Language Teaching lands a significant role as an educational teaching method in enhancing the communicative competence of Electronics Engineering students. Therefore, it is valid that CLT should be integrated in the curriculum to ensure a high level of communication skills in their field of work.

Future research. As indicated in the delimitation of the study, this research solely identifies the communicative competence of the respondents quantitatively. It is recommended to have a further elaboration on the relationship of Engineering students' language proficiency and CLT, as there is a lack of in-depth understanding and description of this phenomena that utilizes a qualitative approach such as focus group and observation. Future researchers may conduct a focus group study that uses an experimental design to comprehensively assess the effectiveness of CLT on developing communicative competence of Engineering students.

References

1. Abides, R. J. (2024). Bridging the skills gap: Examining the electronics technology students' competence and
-

-
- industry demands. *Journal of Interdisciplinary Perspectives*, 2(10). <https://doi.org/10.69569/jip.2024.0407>
2. Acuña-Villacorte, A. (2025). Mechanisms in Regulating Language Practices in Electronics Engineering: A Program Plan for Outcomes-Based Education. *Research Gate*. https://www.researchgate.net/publication/389186716_mechanisms-in-regulating-language-practices-in-electronics-engineering-a-program-plan-for-outcomes-based-education
 3. Badawy, Mazen. (2023). English Language Skills for Engineering Students from the Perspective of the Stakeholders: A Need Analysis Study 2023. 3. 1-30. https://www.researchgate.net/publication/373159745_English_Language_Skills_for_Engineering_Students_from_the_Perspective_of_the_Stakeholders_A_Need_Analysis_Study_2023
 4. Bandhari, P. (2020). What Is Quantitative Research? | Definition, Uses & Methods. *Scribbr*. <https://www.scribbr.com/methodology/quantitative-research/>
 5. Bautista, R. B. A., & Del Valle, J. M. (2023). *Communicative competence and oral language usage of Filipino learners in English*. *International Journal of Educational Management and Development Studies*, 4(1), 1–24. <https://doi.org/10.53378/352957>
 6. Bhandari, P. (2025). What Is Qualitative Research? | Methods & Examples. *Scribbr*. <https://www.scribbr.com/methodology/qualitative-research/>
 7. Bhuiyan, M. S. S. (2019). Requirements of English language courses for engineering students in Bangladesh: Teaching and learning perspectives. *Journal of ELT and Education*, 2(3–4), 81–88. <https://jee-bd.com/wp-content/uploads/2020/01/JEE-24-4-10.pdf>
 8. Caulfield, J. (2023). How to do Thematic Analysis / Step-by-Step Guide & Examples. <https://www.scribbr.com/methodology/thematic-analysis/>
 9. Fauziati, E. (2015). A state of the art of communicative competence theory. *The Journal of English Studies*, 2(2), 78–86. <https://doi.org/10.26555/adjes.v2i2.3991>
 10. Guimaras, J. L. P., & Suganob, J. M. (2025). Task-based language teaching and communicative competence of tertiary learners: Basis for an innovative communication enhancement program. *Ignatian International Journal for Multidisciplinary Research*, 3(1). <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11199449>
 11. Khan, M. E. I., Bhuiyan, M. S. S., & Khan, M. E. I. (2024). Current
-

-
- practices and pitfalls of ELT syllabi for developing engineering students' communicative English in Bangladesh. *MEXTESOL Journal*, 48(2).
<https://www.mextesol.net>
12. Mayavan, L. (2022). Communicative language teaching for enhancing and empowering the language proficiency among engineering students. *International Journal of Creative Research Thoughts*, 10(2), 1–15.
<https://ijcrt.org/papers/IJCRT2210205.pdf>
13. Merza, H. N. M. (2022). English grammar competence of Filipino college freshmen. *Journal of Positive School Psychology*, 6(4), 2949–2958.
<http://journalppw.com>
14. Migallos, K., & Parina, J. C. M. (2023). Core language skills significant among engineering graduates to succeed in the global workplace. *MEXTESOL Journal*, 47(1).
<https://www.mextesol.net>
15. Noor, S., Tajik, O., & Golzar, J. (2022). Simple random sampling. *International Journal of Education & Language Studies*, 1(2), 78–82.
<https://doi.org/10.22034/ijels.2022.162982>
16. Qasserras, L. (2023). Systematic Review of Communicative Language Teaching (CLT) in Language Education: A Balanced Perspective. *European Journal of Education and Pedagogy*, 4(6), 17–23.
<https://doi.org/10.24018/ejedu.2023.4.6.763>
17. Rani, A. & Singh, V. (2023). Engineering Success: The Critical Need for English Proficiency in a Globalized World. *International Journal of Advanced Research in Multidisciplinary*. 1(2), p443-446.
<https://multiresearchjournal.theviews.in/uploads/articles/3-1-12.1.pdf>
18. *Republic Act No. 10533*. (n.d.).
https://lawphil.net/statutes/repacts/ra2013/ra_10533_2013.html
19. Salam, Y, M., & Luksfinanto, Y. (2024). A Comprehensive Review of Communicative Language Teaching (CLT) in Modern Classrooms. *Lingeduca: Journal of Language and Education Studies*, 3(1), 58-70.
<https://doi.org/10.70177/lingeduca.v3i1.1338>
20. Salzinger, J. (2024). Rethinking language teaching for engineering students. In: 10th International Conference on Higher Education Advances (HEAd'24). Valencia, 18-21 June 2024.
<https://doi.org/10.4995/HEAd24.2024.17068>
21. Santos, A., Fernandez, V., & Ilustre, R. (2022). English Language Proficiency in the Philippines: An Overview. *International Journal of English*
-

-
- Language Studies, 4(3), 46-51.
<https://doi.org/10.32996/ijels.2022.4.3.7>
22. Shukla, A. (2024). Enhancing communication skills for engineering students. *International Journal of Fundamental and Multidisciplinary Research*.
<https://www.ijfmr.com/papers/2024/5/28964.pdf>
23. Sitoy, J. S., & Sonsona, R. P. J. V. (2024). Investigating the use of communicative language teaching (CLT) strategies to promote innovative teaching and learning approach. *Jurnal Pendidikan Indonesia*, 13(2), 393–402.
<https://doi.org/10.23887/jpiundiksha.v13i2.79184>
24. Tian, W. (2025). A Comprehensive Literature Review on Communicative Language Teaching (CLT). *Frontiers in Sustainable Development*, 5(3), 197–205.
<https://doi.org/10.54691/90101304>
25. U, V. & John, D. (2017). Integrating CLIL with CLT to develop speaking skills in the engineering classroom. 7. 44-53.
https://www.researchgate.net/publication/319534780_Integrating_CLIL_with_CLT_to_develop_speaking_skills_in_the_engineering_classroom
26. Venkateswara, U. & John, D. (2017). Integrating CLIL with CLT to develop speaking skills in the engineering classroom. *ESP Journal*.
https://www.researchgate.net/publication/319534780_Integrating_CLIL_with_CLT_to_develop_speaking_skills_in_the_engineering_classroom
27. Wang, J. (2023). Factors hindering the implementation of communicative language teaching in secondary vocational schools of science and engineering in China. *English Language Teaching and Linguistics Studies*, 5(2), 12.
<https://doi.org/10.22158/eltls.v5n2p12>
-